

Bibliographic Analysis of Research on 'Online Higher Education' Worldwide: WoS Articles (2005–2025)

Dr. Osman AKARSU¹, Prof. Dr. Fatih MANGIR²

¹Bilecik Şeyh Edebali University, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, Department of Management Information Systems, Bilecik, Türkiye

²Konya Selçuk University, Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, Department of International Trade and Finance, Konya, Türkiye

Received: 20.05.2025 | Accepted: 28.05.2025 | Published: 30.05.2025

*Corresponding Author: Dr. Osman AKARSU

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15552425](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15552425)

Abstract

Original Research Article

This study examines the status of Online Higher Education studies in the literature between 2005 and 2025 by using the Web of Science database with bibliometric analysis methods. We analyzed 346 articles obtained from the WOS database, which contain qualified publications in the field of Online Higher Education and which were obtained as a result of certain constraints. In this study, the VOS viewer, a popular tool, and the Topic Model Approach were used as bibliometric mapping tools. The main contribution of this research to the field is that it is up-to-date research that maps the studies conducted in the context of Higher Education on Online education, which is one of the decentralized educational activities whose use has increased after the COVID-19 pandemic. Based on the data obtained in the study, co-authorship ties revealing the relationship between the authors, citation analysis of prominent authors, citation analysis of countries showing the distribution of the phenomenon on the world geography, citation analysis of the leading institutions in the field of higher education in the world and citation ties between them, keyword analysis and word ties, and bibliometric match analysis of texts and authors. This study provides a comprehensive and holistic assessment of online higher education, which can be considered as the educational model of the future. The study findings were used to analyze the basic structural trends, similarities and differences in the field of online higher education and to develop solution-oriented suggestions by identifying unique and dominant issues under 19 thematic headings.

Keywords: Higher Education Management, Online Higher Education, Online Education, E-Learning, Online Teaching.

Citation: Akarsu, O., & Mangir, F. (2025). Bibliographic analysis of research on 'online higher education' worldwide: WoS articles (2005–2025). *SSR Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(3), 127-139.

1. INTRODUCTION

The transition to Online and distance learning in all its forms has been exponentially accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic. The pandemic is said to have disrupted or challenged the functioning of the three core missions of higher education worldwide (UNESCO, 2022). Countries have not been equally affected by this anomalous situation for which they were caught unprepared. Some countries have been able to adapt faster than others in terms of reshaping their higher education institutions, where they shape the education of human resources, as well as all kinds of resources, in terms of learning competencies and accelerating the transition to distance education systems. Some countries have experienced serious difficulties in transitioning to compulsory Online education. This sudden transition brought up some constraints such as student needs, teacher

and staff shortages, and revealed some obstacles in terms of technological infrastructure, which caused them to fail to manage the process. Marinoni, Van't Land, and Jensen (2020) reported that only 7% of Higher Education Institutions worldwide experienced teaching cancellations during the pandemic, but 24% of Higher Education Institutions in Africa experienced teaching cancellations. The authors noted that the replacement of classroom teaching with Online formats ranged from 29% in Africa to 85% in Europe.

However, despite the importance of the subject in terms of education systems and its difficulties in practice, it is seen that there has not been a comprehensive and holistic evaluation of its development in the academic field, and the potential opportunities created by Online education, especially in the context of higher education, have not been addressed comprehensively. It is known that Online

education has many implications from curriculum to research, from scientific participation to readiness, from legal preparations to governance. Due to the high number of stakeholders affected by education, it has some limitations and challenges both in terms of transition to Online education before the pandemic (Basilaia & Kvavadze, 2020; Ndibalema, 2022) and transition from Online to face-to-face education after the pandemic (Stoian, Fărcașiu, Dragomir, & Gherheș, 2022). Studies examining the state of Online higher education studies in the field are very limited. The importance of addressing this research gap cannot be overstated, because in an environment where scientific knowledge is intensively produced and consumed, such as higher education institutions, the transition to Online education, which is an education model independent of space and time, is not a choice but a necessity due to the evolving conditions of our age. It is intended to draw attention to the fact that the expression “The environment shapes the person” is a valid inference for Online education.

This research examines the status and trends in the literature of articles dealing with the status of Online education in higher education institutions. Bibliometric analysis, which is preferred as a method, is an up-to-date research technique that allows for examination of the current status of a particular research area with quantitative and structural data, and also has the advantages of facilitating the monitoring of scientific trends through visualization software. The study seeks to answer the following four questions:

RQ1) Which are the most cited authors and prominent academic studies among the articles published in the Web of Science database in the field of Online education in higher education between 2005-2025?

RQ2) Which are the academic journals that publish the most studies on Online education in higher education and what is the impact of these journals in the field?

RQ3) What are the main studies, author clusters, affiliations and research groups that stand out as a result of co-citation analysis in the field of Online education in higher education?

RQ4) What are the prominent research themes, key concept clusters and relatively understudied subfields in the publications on Online education in higher education in the Web of Science database?

Based on these research questions, the study aims to conduct a mapping and bibliometric analysis of 346 articles published in the literature between 2005 and 2025 and located in the WOS database within the framework of certain constraints. In line with the determined criteria, data based on quantitative and numerical criteria were obtained through VOS viewer software. The findings obtained present the outputs of the current scientific knowledge produced in this field, such as authors, countries, and cooperation networks that exist in the literature on Online higher education in a holistic sense. In this way, the study advances the existing literature by revealing the collaborations, information flows, and key issues in the field.

This study consists of 5 chapters. The next section discusses the current state of the literature in the field of Online Higher Education comparatively and controversially. In the third section, the methodology or methodology used in this study is explained, and the features and advantages of the bibliometric mapping tool are mentioned. Information about the nature and scope of the data obtained in the study is provided. In the fourth chapter, the findings of the study are presented systematically, and the status of Online higher education research in the literature is presented based on the field-mapped data, and common links and analyses are revealed. In the conclusion, the findings of the study are evaluated concerning the current literature, and the study concludes with a discussion on the limitations of the study and potential study topics.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

We all know that technology has shaped and transformed educational environments as well as every field. However, although Online and Online teaching and learning have been an important research topic for the last thirty years, it is stated in the literature that studies on Online education programs in universities are still insufficient (Hofer, Nistor, & Scheibenzuber, 2021). Although it seems to have lost its importance relatively after the COVID-19 pandemic, which we call the new normal, it is essential to develop and improve Online education in preparation for potential future crises. When we look at the studies conducted for these reasons, it is seen that the related literature has diversified into different specific areas. There is a clustering of studies on Online learning environments in higher education institutions (Broadbent & Poon, 2015; Moore, Dickson-Deane, & Galyen, 2011; Reese, 2015), designing blended learning environments (Müller & Mildemberger, 2021), students' perspectives on Online education (Hung & Chou, 2015; Palmer & Holt, 2010), educators' views on Online education environments (Rahayu & Wirza, 2020; Rashid, Shukor, Tasir, & Na, 2021).

In addition to this, it is noteworthy that the issue of access to Online higher education is addressed in the literature (Lee, 2017; Seale, 2013), and that there are challenges and problems (Goddard & Puukka, 2008) in terms of its management and leadership (Burnette, 2015).

It is seen that the phenomenon is also evaluated from perspectives such as the status of Online higher education in terms of communication and information technologies (Heinze & Procter, 2006; Pinto et al., 2012), advantages and disadvantages of distance education and e-learning adoption in higher education (Arkorful & Abaidoo, 2015). There are many studies in the literature where Online education is naturally associated with the pandemic (W. Ali, 2020; Mishra, Gupta, & Shree, 2020; Turnbull, Chugh, & Luck, 2021). It is seen that the phenomenon includes subdivisions such as infrastructure support, personnel preparation, accessibility of students, and the realization of education within this cluster.

In line with the general trend of the literature, it has been observed that Online higher education studies, especially

in the post-pandemic period, have been handled in line with the discourses of the Socio-Technical theory put forward by Bostrom and Heinen (1977). In their model, the authors describe a work system as being made up of two separate yet interconnected systems: the social system and the technical system. The technical system focuses on the processes, tasks, and technologies needed to convert inputs into outputs, while the social system centers around

people's characteristics (such as attitudes, skills, and values), the relationships between individuals, reward structures, and patterns of authority. The study assumes that the outcomes produced by the work system emerge from the dynamic interaction between these two systems. Based on the theoretical expansion potential of these assumptions about the model, a visualization of the Online Higher Education Model is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Online Higher Education Model

Source: Adapted from Bostrom and Heinen (1977, p. 25) and created by the authors.

Within the social subsystems, the institutional structure of universities and the people in which stakeholders are addressed are named as components, and within the technical subsystems, LMSs (Aldiab, Chowdhury, Kootsookos, Alam, & Allhibi, 2019), which are called

learning management systems in the literature, and education and training process and support activities are conceptualized. Table 1 presents an evaluation of the model in the context of Online Higher Education within the framework of Socio-Technical theory.

Table 1. An Evaluation in the Context of Online Higher Education

Systems	Components	(An Evaluation in the Context of Online Higher Education)
Social Subsystems	Structure	It is the organizational structure of a higher education institution. In Online higher education, the organization of virtual campuses includes elements such as departmental structure, job descriptions, reporting relationships, and Online academic units.
	People	It refers to human resources such as students, teaching staff, support staff, and administrators. In the Online environment, individuals' motivation, digital competencies, and interaction skills are important.
Technical Subsystems	Technology	It includes technical infrastructure such as Online education platforms (learning management systems), virtual classroom software, mobile applications, and learning analytics tools. This technology is the cornerstone of the learning experience.
	Process	Instructional processes include activities such as content development, assessment methods, and student support systems. In Online education, these processes are carried out in a digital environment and require continuous improvement.

Source: Adapted from Bostrom and Heinen (1977, p. 25) and created by the authors.

As emphasized in the core of the theory, these components are interrelated (Bostrom & Heinen, 1977). Although this model does not address the general trends in the Online higher education literature (Ali, Wood-Harper, & Wood, 2024; Li, Li, & Cai, 2021; Wang, Solan, & Ghods, 2010; White, White, & Borthwick, 2021), it is important in terms of its compatibility with the discourses of the theory in terms of the objective reality they reveal. In this study, the existing literature is discussed controversially, and it is intended to be associated with the existing theoretical infrastructure without going beyond the scope of the study.

3. METHODOLOGY

Bibliometric

analysis employs descriptive indicators regarding publications, such as authors, institutions, journals, keywords, disciplines, and citations, to construct knowledge networks and maps for a specific field of research. But it also uses advanced text mining techniques to reveal research themes and potential areas of future research (Ziegler, 2009). This part of the research explains the purpose of the research, the analysis, and the findings.

3.1. Purpose of the Study

As a result of quantitative data and numerical measurement indicators' bibliometric analysis of the term "Online higher education," it is aimed at presenting the studies on the term to the attention of researchers with a holistic perspective.

3.2. Data and Analysis

The Web of Science (WoS) platform was chosen as a source of data for this literature review. WoS is considered to be one of the most comprehensive and multidisciplinary databases presents in scientific literature and is extensively used by researchers globally. Several tools for bibliometric analysis were employed in the literature. In the current study, the VOSviewer program was preferred owing to its merits with respect to functionality. It is regarded as a significant program that facilitates researchers to identify evolutions, relationships, and new concepts in literature more easily. Furthermore, it enables analyzing data sets extensively since it supports visualization, mapping, and multi-dimensional analysis. Topic modeling approaches, which include machine learning and statistical research, are developed to detect word trends in documents. Topic modeling analyses concepts rather than individual words. Topic modeling is a powerful technique in the field of natural language processing (NLP) that helps to identify hidden topics in large text corpora. LDA, latent semantic analysis (LSA), non-negative matrix factorization (NMF), and BERTopic are four popular methods widely used in the literature (Wallach et al., 2009: 1763). In this study, Latent Dirichlet Allocation method is used.

The familiarization of the research with the data, the screening process, and the inclusion and exclusion criteria was carried out by taking some issues into consideration. The choice of the Web of Science database in this study for various types of analyses, especially bibliometric analyses, is of the utmost significance regarding the validity of the research. Equipped with its advanced search indicators and various control mechanisms, this database facilitates sophisticated analysis of data and comprises quality and reliable studies from the viewpoint of publication ethics. It also allows access to a wide range of data covering an array of disciplines. To this extent, 346 papers were found after conducting a search in Web of Science on April 20, 2025, using the words "Online higher education" in the "all fields" category.

By years, 238 journal articles, 57 papers, 27 review articles, 25 book chapters, 11 editorial contents, 2 book types, 2 books, 2 book reviews, and 1 meeting abstract across various disciplines, between the years 2005 to 2025. By disciplines, the majority of the studies were in education (269), followed by computer science (62), economics and business administration (21), engineering (17), environmental science (10), communication (5), psychology (11), chemistry (2), geography (2), multidisciplinary material science (2), applied physics (2), field studies, astronomy, audiology, clinical neurology, ecology, linguistics, logic, medicine, multidisciplinary fields, nursing, public administration, urban planning, sociology, social issues and sports. Data were analyzed through author-citation-journal-country-institution and keyword analysis. Indexed material in Web of Science was utilized as a database.

4. FINDINGS

Having a vision of post-pandemic articles worldwide, answers to the research questions were looked for in this section, where articles of diverse disciplines were retrieved from the Web of Science database. In here, the results that express the situation of bibliometric analysis of the Online Higher Education phenomenon in the literature are presented.

4.1. Co-Authorship of Authors

Based on the co-authorship analysis, a network map was generated by setting the criteria of at least one publication and one citation to highlight the authors with the strongest connections and collaborations. The analysis also reveals which authors have received the highest number of citations. Jaclyn Broadbent and WL Poon with 874 citations, Anna Sun and Chen Xiufang with 282 citations, lui zeng and pengcheng jiao with 267 citations are not the most connected authors. Notably, the authors with the highest number of publications do not rank among the most interconnected authors within the network (Julio Meneses, Roldan Guerrero, Elena Ana and Mitchell Peters, respectively).

Figure 1. Co-author Links Demonstrating Collaboration between Authors

4. 2. Citation of Authors

To find citation networks, an author citation network chart was created on the basis of a minimum of 1 publication

and a minimum of 1 citation. The most cited authors are Jaclyn Broadbent and WL Poon with 874, Anna Sun and Chen Xiufang with 282, lui zeng and pengcheng jiao with 267 citations.

Figure 2. Authors' Citation Ties

4. 3. Citation of Countries

To construct a citation network map based on countries of origin, 49 observation units with interconnections were analyzed, using the criteria that each country must have published at least one work and received at least one citation. The analysis shows that the

countries with the highest citation counts are the United States (1582 citations), Spain (674 citations), and China (317 citations). By overall link strength, the USA and Spain come first, followed by China at 9th position. On the criteria of number of publications, the order is: USA (108 publications), Spain (72 publications), and Australia (23 publications).

Figure 3. Citation Ties of Countries

4. 4. Citation of Organizations,

To create an inter-institutional citation network diagram, 273 observation

units were examined based on the relationship between them under the condition of having published at least 1 work and having been cited at least once by an institution.

Figure 4. Citation Links of Institutions

Institutions such as Univ Oberta de Catalunya (23 publications), Open Univ Catalunya (15 publications), and Univ Aberta (6 publications) are among the most represented in terms of publication volume. However, the institutions associated with the most highly cited works are Deakin University (889 citations), Purdue University (307 citations), and Rowan University (282 citations).

4. 5. Co-occurrence of All Keywords

If we take the most frequently used words that appear in articles on Online higher, online higher education with 78, higher education with 69, Online learning with 54, Online education with 40 and e-learning with 19 repetitions.

Figure 7. Links Between co-cited Authors

4. 8. Topic Models Obtained in Online Higher Education Field (15 Topic, LDA Analysis, Coherence Optimum)

This study aims to reveal current structural trends, main problem areas and development focuses in higher education by systematically analyzing the existing literature in the field of Online higher education using Topic Model Approaches. The primary reason for selecting this method in the study is that empirical evidence supports its superior effectiveness in measuring the semantic coherence of topics compared to alternative approaches. Deveaud et al. (2014) method enhances the distinction between topic distributions by maximizing information differences, which leads to a clearer and more meaningful emergence of topics. This characteristic is

especially crucial for improving the performance of topic modeling, particularly in large-scale text datasets. Deveaud’s metric, empirically identified as the most effective, was therefore chosen to determine the optimal number of topics and is illustrated in Figure 8. Initially, the data was imported from the file into a dataframe using pandas, and the "Abstract" and "Title" columns were cleaned by removing stopwords and additional non-informative words (e.g., "findings," "study," "data," etc.). This cleaning process was essential to ensure that the LDA model operated with a more meaningful and refined vocabulary. Subsequently, a dictionary was constructed from the cleaned texts using the Gensim library, and a corpus was generated to create the document-word matrix necessary for the LDA model. Figure 8 shows the optimal topic determination metrics with Latent Dirichlet Allocation.

Figure 8. Examining Optimal Topic Determination Metrics with LDA

Source: Created by the authors.

Online higher education has led to significant transformations in the field of education with the development of digital technologies. New research areas have emerged in many dimensions, from students' learning experiences to the new roles of faculty members, from quality assurance to student support systems. In this study, thematic analysis was conducted using the topic modeling approach in order to understand the trends in Online higher education in the literature. The findings systematically

classify the prominent themes in the Online higher education literature and provide a comprehensive map of current research areas. Thus, both the current knowledge base has been revealed and potential directions for future research have been determined.

Table 2 shows 15 Topic Models Obtained in Online Higher Education Field by using in LDA Analysis, and coherence optimum model.

Table 2. 15 Topic Models Obtained in Online Higher Education

Topic No	Thematic Title	Featured Keywords	Short Description
0	Student Data and Mentoring	students, Online, undergraduate, data, faculty, research, mentoring	Data usage, mentoring and academic support studies in undergraduate students.
1	International Students and Engagement	Online, students, international, education, higher, learning, engagement, learners	International students and participation processes in Online higher education.
2	Gamification and the Learning Experience	students, gamification, degree, Online, education, use, changes	The effect of gamification on student experience and academic progress.
3	Physical Activity and Learning from Home	physical, teachers, fitness, home, classes, female, video, networks, exchange	Learning from home models and social interaction in physical education.
4	Online Education Policies	education, Online, higher, study, teaching, systems	Structural frameworks and policies in Online education.
5	Creative Thinking and Performance	Online, learning, student, students, model, thinking, performance, courses	The relationship between creative thinking and academic success in Online environments.
6	Course Design and Student Centeredness	learning, Online, education, higher, course, design, student, study	Student-centered learning design and course development processes.
7	Social Learning and Student Experience	learning, Online, students, education, higher, study, social, teaching	The place of social interactions in Online student experience.
8	Academic Success and Outcomes	Online, students, academic, learning, higher, study, results, education	Factors and outcomes of academic success in Online learning.
9	Technology Use and Social Presence	Online, learning, students, social, technology, research, presence	The contribution of technology to the sense of social presence in Online learning.
10	Support Systems and Time Management	students, Online, course, education, time, support, social, student	Student support systems and time management strategies.
11	Course Management and University Processes	Online, education, students, learning, study, higher, courses, university	Adaptation of Online course management and university processes.
12	Digitalization in the Education System	Online, education, higher, students, learning, study, teaching, research	Digital transformation and new learning models in higher education.
13	Community Engagement and Literature Evaluation	education, Online, higher, research, community, review	Online community participation and academic literature reviews.
14	Digital Gamification and Learning	learning, gamification, digital, education, higher, elements, game, Online	Digital gamification applications in education and their effects on learning processes.

Source: Created by the authors. **Note:** Thematic headings are listed in order of importance.

The findings of the study show that Online higher education literature is mainly shaped around learning experience, student success and instructor roles. In addition, it has been observed that more specific themes such as quality assessment processes, student support mechanisms and international perspectives are increasingly gaining importance. This thematic structure provides important clues about the directions in which the field can deepen in the future. It has been concluded that more holistic approaches and interdisciplinary studies are needed to increase sustainable quality and student success in Online education. Future research can further enrich this field by focusing especially on regional differences and digital pedagogical innovations.

This table can be grouped under the following conclusions.

1. Learning Experience in Online Higher Education in General

Students' learning experiences, teaching processes and research activities are among the main topics in online higher education. Student motivation, time management and the effects of technology on learning are discussed under this heading. In addition, general evaluations are made regarding the roles of faculty members and students in digital environments.

2. Student Success, Participation and Interaction

Student participation levels, commitment and success rates in online education are a critical area of research. Student interaction, course attendance rates and dropout rates stand out in this theme. Evaluation methods, student satisfaction and strategies for increasing academic performance are also examined in this group.

3. Faculty Members, Instructors and Their Roles

The changing roles of faculty members in online higher education, the digital competencies they must have and performance evaluation criteria are an important topic of discussion. Instructors' course design, student interaction management and effective use of technology skills are gathered under this heading. In addition, the effect of instructor-student interaction on learning outcomes is also investigated.

4. Student Support Mechanisms and Communities

Support services, mentoring programs and learning communities offered to students in online education environments are elements that directly affect students' success. Under this heading, the design of support systems, methods to increase student engagement and community building practices are discussed.

5. International Perspectives and Regional Approaches

Regional and cultural differences in online higher education lead to differentiation of education policies and practices. In particular, practices in developing regions such as Africa and international education narratives and

pedagogical support models are evaluated within the scope of this theme.

6. Quality, Evaluation and Academic Standards

Quality assurance, evaluation processes and protection of academic standards in online higher education have an important place in the literature. Differences in experience between face-to-face and online education, student satisfaction and educational quality criteria are examined under this heading.

When a general evaluation of the themes and dominant topics obtained with the Topic Model Approach is made, it is found that the most dominant studies in the literature are the Online Education Structure in countries. Student support mechanisms and efforts to increase participation form a separate group. There is an emphasis on the roles of teaching staff and the quality of education. Dropout and factors affecting success are the focus of certain studies. Continental/demographic differences (Africa etc.) and international perspectives are emphasized, technology integration and new competence requirements are also created as an axis, and finally, the existence of a small group with a special focus on the differences between physical and online environments is evident.

5. CONCLUSION and DISCUSSION

It has been found that thematic headings obtained with the Topic Model Approach include various focuses in terms of future studies. Digital transformation and data-based education in online higher education regarding digitalization, data use and research-oriented changes, Quality and Performance in Online Higher Education regarding quality assessment of online higher education applications and student performances, Student Experience and Academic Processes regarding students' adaptation to academic processes and experiences in online learning, Time Management and Social Learning Dynamics regarding students' time management, teacher interaction and social learning in online environments, Online Higher Education Policies and Structural Frameworks regarding the general structure of the online higher education system, policies and teaching models, Support Systems and Student Satisfaction regarding student support services, satisfaction and success factors in online learning, Online course design, technology use and improvement of learning experience regarding Learning Design and Technology Integration reveal a general tendency in the literature.

The findings of this study, which aims to map the field of Online higher education, are discussed comparatively and controversially in this section concerning the literature. This study used domain mapping methods such as co-author ties, citation analysis, and citation ties, which indicate collaborations between authors. These three science mapping techniques focus on the authors. In the first stage, a quantitative analysis of the metadata was conducted to reveal the distribution of publications by years, universities, countries, authors, journals, and research fields.

Countries such as the USA, Spain, Australia, and China produce more publications (Table 3). In addition to these, countries such as the UK, Portugal, Ireland, Mexico, the Netherlands, and Saudi Arabia can be listed among those that stand out, albeit relatively low. When these results are compared, it is seen that although the USA is among the countries that publish more articles, it lags behind Spain in the most cited countries. Other studies in the literature with similar findings but using different databases also show that the United States and the United Kingdom have more publications than other countries (Sudakova et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022, p. 626).

Australia's Deakin University receives more citations than the US and Spanish Universities. Jaelyn Broadbent and WL Poon, faculty members at this institution, are also among the most cited authors. The reason why the authors' article on self-regulated learning strategies and academic achievement in higher education learning environments is highly cited can be interpreted as making valid inferences about how to better apply Online learning strategies, especially in the context of higher education (Broadbent & Poon, 2015). The address institutions of the most cited publications are from two universities in Australia and the USA, respectively. It is seen that universities that publish more articles do not always overlap with the most cited universities.

When the study findings are evaluated in terms of higher education institutions, it is seen that Spanish universities, Univ Oberta de Catalunya (23 works), Open Univ Cataluña (15 works), and Univ Aberta (6) are represented (Figure 4). The reason for these findings is that these universities are universities that continue their education and training activities with the Open Education System, suggesting that publications come from within a focused field of study.

Among the findings on the most frequently used keywords obtained in the study, the presence of a group that focuses mostly on knowledge creation processes, such as learner analytics, inclusion of students, co-creation of knowledge, lived experience, etc., is itself. In addition, it is seen that critical thinking, data mining are among the frequently used word links in sub-fields such as critical thinking and data mining. Other sub-clusters, such as lifelong learning, adult education, and international and refugee education, are noteworthy. Another sub-cluster, which can also be called the digital cluster, is based on the sustainability-based, technological, and digital transformation of the phenomenon. Another cluster shows us that it is also shaped around assessment tools in terms of the electronicization of measurement tools. Social media and virtual platforms contain another of the most frequently used keyword ties in Online higher education. At the individual analysis level, the phenomenon was found to be handled within another cluster, such as motivation, personalized education, character, and academic performance.

In the current literature, there are studies that address the phenomenon of Online Higher Education with similar bibliometric analyses (Fauzi, 2022; Sudakova et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2022). The findings of these studies also

overlap with the findings of our study. However, it is seen that these studies focus on certain breakdowns in terms of geographical distinction, content or focus, and do not make an evaluation of the entire phenomenon in a holistic sense.

In addition, the study findings contain similar results with the groupings in similar study findings in the literature. Bibliometric studies on Online higher education mostly focused on the responses of higher education institutions to Online education during COVID-19 (Fauzi, 2022; Zhang et al., 2022), bibliometric analyses on virtual reality in higher education (Rojas-Sánchez, Palos-Sánchez, & Folgado-Fernández, 2023), and studies on the use of artificial intelligence (Crompton & Burke, 2023; Ouyang, Zheng, & Jiao, 2022). It has been stated that artificial intelligence in the field of education, especially in higher education, can contribute to the change of education through “automation of administrative teaching tasks, software programs that support personalized education, identification of topics that need to be reinforced in the classroom, guidance and support of students outside the classroom” and the intelligent use of data to teach and support students (Lucena, Díaz, Rodríguez, & Marín, 2019, p. 1).

The most fundamental contribution of this study to the field is that it addresses a general map of the field using the Topic Model Approach, a relatively new method, and Vosviewer, a powerful and proven bibliometric analysis tool. Another important contribution is that it provides a rich perspective for subsequent studies in the field of Online Higher Education. Apart from the bibliometric analysis findings of this study, the Online Higher Education Model expressed in Figure and Table 1 has been introduced to the literature. It is expected that this model will serve as a theoretical framework in subsequent studies.

5.1. Limitations of the Study and Recommendations for Future Studies

As in every study, this study has some limitations. Among these, the most common limitation, especially in bibliometric analyses, is the scope issue. The use of only Web of Science data in this study is a limitation, and the absence of Scopus data is a limitation. However, there are studies in the literature on Online higher education based on the Scopus database (Phan, Vu, Doan, Luong, & Bui, 2022; Sudakova et al., 2022). For this reason, the Web of Science database was preferred in the design and data collection stages of this study. Another limitation of the study is that publications accepted to the Web of Science database but not added to the index are naturally excluded from the scope. The search terms used in this study can also be expressed as another limitation. Although it is desired to increase inclusiveness in terms of the use of synonyms, the terms education, higher education, and Online may have been addressed from different perspectives in the literature.

In subsequent studies, especially adaptation to Online higher education after COVID-19, mixed or hybrid systems (face-to-face - Online) can be studied on their effects. An assessment can be made that takes into account the conditions of the countries. The effects of technology

adaptation ability at the point of transition to Online Higher Education can be addressed with quantitative analyses. An assessment of the subject in the context of artificial intelligence integration can be expressed as another recommended field of study.

REFERENCES

- Aldiab, A., Chowdhury, H., Kootsookos, A., Alam, F., & Allhibi, H. (2019). Utilization of Learning Management Systems (LMSs) in higher education system: A case review for Saudi Arabia. *Energy Procedia*, 160, 731-737. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2019.02.186>
- Ali, M., Wood-Harper, T., & Wood, B. (2024). Understanding the technical and social paradoxes of learning management systems usage in higher education: A sociotechnical perspective. *Systems Research and Behavioral Science*, 41(1), 134-152. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sres.2945>
- Ali, W. (2020). Online and remote learning in higher education institutes: A necessity in light of COVID-19 pandemic. *Higher Education Studies*, 10(3), 16-25. <https://doi.org/10.5539/hes.v10n3p16>
- Arkorful, V., & Abaidoo, N. (2015). The role of e-learning, advantages and disadvantages of its adoption in higher education. *International Journal of Instructional Technology and Distance Learning*, 12(1), 29-42. https://www.itdl.org/Journal/Jan_15/Jan15.pdf#page=33
- Basilaia, G., & Kvavadze, D. (2020). Transition to Online education in schools during a SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic in Georgia. *Pedagogical Research*, 5(4). <https://doi.org/10.29333/pr/7937>
- Bostrom, R. P., & Heinen, J. S. (1977). MIS problems and failures: A socio-technical perspective. Part I: The causes. *MIS quarterly*, 17-32. <https://doi.org/10.2307/248710>
- Broadbent, J., & Poon, W. L. (2015). Self-regulated learning strategies & academic achievement in Online higher education learning environments: A systematic review. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 27, 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2015.04.007>
- Burnette, D. M. (2015). Strategies for Effective Online Education Administrative Leadership in Higher Education Institutions. *Quarterly Review of Distance Education: Volume 16, Number 3, 2015*, 16(3), 13-25. <https://124.im/WYDT>
- Crompton, H., & Burke, D. (2023). Artificial intelligence in higher education: the state of the field. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 20(1), 22. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00392-8>
- Deveaud, R., SanJuan, E., & Bellot, P. (2014). Accurate and effective latent concept modeling for ad hoc information retrieval. *Document Numérique*, 17(1), 61-84. <https://doi.org/10.3166/dn.17.1.61-84>
- Fauzi, M. A. (2022). E-learning in higher education institutions during COVID-19 pandemic: current and future trends through bibliometric analysis. *Heliyon*, 8(5). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2022.e09433>
- Goddard, J., & Puukka, J. (2008). The engagement of higher education institutions in regional development: An overview of the opportunities and challenges. *Higher Education Management And Policy*, 20(2), 11-41. <https://doi.org/10.1787/hemp-v20-art9-en>
- Heinze, A., & Procter, C. (2006). Online communication and information technology education. *Journal of Information Technology Education: Research*, 5(1), 235-249. <https://doi.org/10.28945/245>
- Hofer, S. I., Nistor, N., & Scheibenzuber, C. (2021). Online teaching and learning in higher education: Lessons learned in crisis situations. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 121, 106789. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2021.106789>
- Hung, M.-L., & Chou, C. (2015). Students' perceptions of instructors' roles in blended and Online learning environments: A comparative study. *Computers & Education*, 81, 315-325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2014.10.022>
- Lee, K. (2017). Rethinking the accessibility of Online higher education: A historical review. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 33, 15-23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2017.01.001>
- Li, Y., Li, X., & Cai, J. (2021). How attachment affects user stickiness on live streaming platforms: A socio-technical approach perspective. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 60, 102478. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2021.102478>
- Lucena, F. J. H., Díaz, I. A., Rodríguez, J. M. R., & Marín, J. A. M. (2019). Influencia del aula invertida en el rendimiento académico. Una revisión sistemática. *Campus Virtuales*, 8(1), 9-18. <https://124.im/BxQb6IU>
- Marinoni, G., Van't Land, H., & Jensen, T. (2020). The impact of Covid-19 on higher education around the world. *IAU Global Survey Report*, 23(1), 1-17. <https://124.im/ImhTe>
- Mishra, L., Gupta, T., & Shree, A. (2020). Online teaching-learning in higher education during lockdown period of COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, 1, 100012. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedro.2020.100012>
- Moore, J. L., Dickson-Deane, C., & Galyen, K. (2011). e-Learning, Online learning, and distance learning environments: Are they the same? *The Internet And Higher Education*, 14(2), 129-135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iheduc.2010.10.001>
- Müller, C., & Mildemberger, T. (2021). Facilitating flexible learning by replacing classroom time with an Online learning environment: A systematic review of blended learning in higher education. *Educational Research Review*, 34,

100394. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2021.100394>
- Ndibalema, P. (2022). Constraints of transition to Online distance learning in Higher Education Institutions during COVID-19 in developing countries: A systematic review. *E-learning and Digital Media*, 19(6), 595-618. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20427530221107510>
- Ouyang, F., Zheng, L., & Jiao, P. (2022). Artificial intelligence in Online higher education: A systematic review of empirical research from 2011 to 2020. *Education and Information Technologies*, 27(6), 7893-7925. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-10925-9>
- Palmer, S., & Holt, D. (2010). Students' perceptions of the value of the elements of an Online learning environment: Looking back in moving forward. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 18(2), 135-151. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09539960802364592>
- Phan, T.-T. T., Vu, C.-T., Doan, P.-T. T., Luong, D.-H., & Bui, T.-P. (2022). Two decades of studies on learning management system in higher education: A bibliometric analysis with Scopus database 2000-2020. *Journal of University Teaching and Learning Practice*, 19(3), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.53761/1.19.3.17>
- Pinto, M., Souza, F., Nogueira, F., Balula, A., Pedro, L., Pombo, L., . . . Moreira, A. (2012). Tracing the use of communication technology in higher education: a literature review. *INTED2012 Proceedings*, 850-859. <https://doi.org/10.124.im/n2ZA>
- Rahayu, R. P., & Wirza, Y. (2020). Teachers' perception of Online learning during pandemic covid-19. *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan*, 20(3), 392-406. <https://doi.org/10.17509/jpp.v20i3.29226>
- Rashid, A. H. A., Shukor, N. A., Tasir, Z., & Na, K. S. (2021). Teachers' Perceptions and Readiness toward the Implementation of Virtual Learning Environment. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 10(1), 209-214. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v10i1.21014>
- Reese, S. A. (2015). Online learning environments in higher education: Connectivism vs. dissociation. *Education and Information Technologies*, 20, 579-588. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-013-9303-7>
- Rojas-Sánchez, M. A., Palos-Sánchez, P. R., & Folgado-Fernández, J. A. (2023). Systematic literature review and bibliometric analysis on virtual reality and education. *Education and Information Technologies*, 28(1), 155-192. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11167-5>
- Seale, J. (2013). *E-learning and disability in higher education: Accessibility research and practice*: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.124.im/MjIP>
- Stoian, C. E., Fărcașiu, M. A., Dragomir, G.-M., & Gherheș, V. (2022). Transition from Online to face-to-face education after COVID-19: The benefits of Online education from students' perspective. *Sustainability*, 14(19), 12812. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su141912812>
- Sudakova, N. E., Savina, T. N., Masalimova, A. R., Mikhaylovsky, M. N., Karandeeva, L. G., & Zhdanov, S. P. (2022). Online formative assessment in higher education: Bibliometric analysis. *Education Sciences*, 12(3), 209. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci12030209>
- Turnbull, D., Chugh, R., & Luck, J. (2021). Transitioning to E-Learning during the COVID-19 pandemic: How have Higher Education Institutions responded to the challenge? *Education and Information Technologies*, 26(5), 6401-6419. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10633-w>
- UNESCO. (2022). *Higher education global data report*. Retrieved from A contribution to the World Higher Education Conference 18-20 May 2022: <https://doi.org/10.124.im/SKyga>
- Wallach, H., Mimno, D., & McCallum, A. (2009). Rethinking LDA: Why priors matter. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 22. <https://doi.org/10.3115/1699571.1699627>
- Wang, J., Solan, D., & Ghods, A. (2010). Distance learning success—a perspective from socio-technical systems theory. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 29(3), 321-329. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01449290903544645>
- White, S., White, S., & Borthwick, K. (2021). Blended professionals, technology and Online learning: Identifying a socio-technical third space in higher education. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 75(1), 161-174. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hequ.12252>
- Zhang, L., Carter Jr, R. A., Qian, X., Yang, S., Rujimora, J., & Wen, S. (2022). Academia's responses to crisis: A bibliometric analysis of literature on Online learning in higher education during COVID-19. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 53(3), 620-646. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjjet.13191>
- Ziegler, B. E. (2009). *Methods for bibliometric analysis of research: renewable energy case study*. Massachusetts Institute of Technology. <https://dspace.mit.edu/handle/1721.1/61289>